

Kinetics and Mechanism of Osmium (VIII) Catalyzed Oxidation of Thiocyanate with Potassium Hexacyanoferrate (III) in Aqueous Alkaline Medium.

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The kinetics of Osmium(VIII) catalysed electron transfer reaction between thiocyanate and alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) at 35° has been investigated. Potassium chloride which was used as the background indifferent electrolyte has shown a positive salt effect on the rate of the reaction. Specific cationic effect was found with catalytic order of $K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$. The experimental data indicates the rate law,

$$-d[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] / dt = k [Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] [OH^-] [Os(VIII)]$$

and a suitable mechanism has been proposed. The products of the reaction have little effect on the pseudo first order constant. An average value of enthalpy of activation for the overall reaction was found to be 18.0 ± 0.5 Kcal/mole.

SOLYMOSI et al¹⁻³ found that Osmium(VIII) is a catalyst in the oxidation of a number of organic and inorganic substrates by potassiumhexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium. A survey of the literature reveals that the course of oxidation of an organic substrate⁴⁻¹⁴ involves the formation of an Os(III)-substrate complex with subsequent reduction to Os(VI) and the catalyst being regenerated in a fast step by the oxidant. In the oxidation of tellurium (IV)¹⁵, the zero order with respect to the substrate was explained by proposing an intermediate binuclear complex between the oxidant and Osmium(VIII) followed by the redox reaction. The rate law indicating the first order with respect to substrate, oxidant, catalyst and hydroxide in the oxidation of Se(IV)¹⁶ is consistent with a mechanism involving the formation of Se(V) as an intermediate in the reversible rate determining step followed by its fast oxidation to Se(VI) by Osmium(VIII). The catalyst is regenerated in a subsequent fast oxidation of Os(VII) by hexacyanoferrate(III). In the present study, the oxidation of thiocyanate with alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) has been carried out in order to investigate the mechanistic course of the reaction in the light of the proposed three schemes of mechanism. Oxidation of thiocyanate by Cr(VI)^{17,18} and V(V)¹⁹ involves six electron change to form sulphate and cyanide. But its oxidation with permanganate²⁰, hydrogen peroxide²¹, and peroxomonosulphate²² involves eight electron change to produce sulphate and cyanate.

Our preliminary experiments (Table 1) on the stoichiometry of the Osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of thiocyanate in presence of twenty times molar excess of hexacyanoferrate (III) in alkaline medium are in good agreement with the results of Suseela²³, conforming to

the eight electron oxidation of the substrate

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRY OF THE REACTION.

[Os(VIII)] = 1.0×10^{-4} M ; [OH ⁻] = 2.0 M		
10 ⁴ [SCN ⁻], M	[Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻], M	[Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻]/[SCN ⁻]
Taken	Consumed	
9.74	0.078	8.01
25.14	0.202	8.04
40.02	0.316	8.90
58.45	0.468	8.01
75.16	0.602	8.01

Experimental

E. Merck. (G. R. grade) samples of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III), potassium thiocyanate, potassium hydroxide and potassium chloride were employed. Osmium(VIII) solution was prepared from Osmium tetroxide (Johnson Matthey & Co., London) in 0.5 M potassium hydroxide solution to minimize the volatility of the metal ion²⁴. The Osmium(VIII) was determined iodometrically to the starch end point²⁵. Other reagents used were also of analytical grade. All the solutions were prepared in triple distilled water.

Aqueous solution of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) was stored in dark amber coloured bottles to avoid photochemical reaction²⁶, but the solutions older than 100 hrs. were not used²⁷. Aqueous solutions of thiocyanate were stable for more than a month²⁸.

Kinetic studies were made at constant temperature of $35.00 \pm 0.05^\circ$, unless otherwise mentioned and at constant ionic strength of $2.0M$, adjusted with potassium chloride as indifferent background electrolyte. All the solutions were allowed to reach the temperature equilibrium by keeping them in a thermostat and the reactant solutions were mixed externally, potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) being the last component added to initiate the reaction. Keeping thiocyanate and alkali concentration always in excess, the progress of the reaction was monitored by estimating the residual concentration of hexacyanoferrate (III). The reaction mixture was quenched by adding an aliquot to a solution of total volume of 60 ml. containing 20ml. of 10% potassium iodide, 10 ml. of 20% zinc sulphate solution and sufficient volume of $5.0N$ sulphuric acid to give an overall acidity of $0.05N$ after neutralizing the alkali content of reaction mixture. The liberated iodine was titrated with standard sodium thiosulphate solution to the starch end point.

Results and Discussion

Plots of \log (oxidant) versus time yield a straight line indicating the order with respect to the oxidant to be one. Potassium sulphate and potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) initially added, were found to have no effect. The pseudo first order rate constants remained constant over the concentration range of $(2.5 - 7.5) \times 10^{-3}M$ hexacyanoferrate (III) and they were calculated from the slopes of the linear portions of the plots. The results were reproducible to 2-3%. Under the experimental conditions the uncatalyzed reaction appears to be very slow.

A variation of Os(VIII) concentration in the range of $0.25 \times 10^{-5} - 1.20 \times 10^{-5}$ shows that the reaction is first order in Osmium(VIII) (Table 2). About thirtyfold variation in the concentration of thiocyanate shows that the rate is independent of its concentration (Table 3). The constant values of the second order rate constants ($k/[OH^-]$) in the last column of the Table 4 shows first order behaviour with respect to the concentration of alkali.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF OSMIUM(VIII) CONCENTRATION.

$[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[SCN^-] = 4.64 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[OH^-] = 0.50 M$, $\mu = 2.0$, $T = 35^\circ$

$10^5[Os(VIII)], M$	$10^8 k(\text{observed})$ (min^{-1})	$10^2 k(\text{observed})$ [Os(VIII)] $M^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$
0.25	0.31	1.21
0.50	0.61	1.21
0.80	1.01	1.25
1.00	1.21	1.21
1.20	1.54	1.28

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF THIOCYANATE

$[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[OH^-] = 0.50 M$; $\mu = 2.0$. (A) $[Os(VIII)] = 1.2 \times 10^{-5} M$; Temp. 35° ; (B) $[Os(VIII)] = 5.8 \times 10^{-6} M$ Temp. 35° ; (C) $[Os(VIII)] = 4.8 \times 10^{-6} M$; Temp. 45°

$10^2(SC \ 10^8 k(\text{min}^{-1})$ N-)M ^(A)	$10^2(SC \ 10^4 k(\text{min}^{-1})$ N-)M ^(B)	$10^2(SC \ 10^3 k(\text{min}^{-1})$ N-)M ^(C)			
4.64	1.52	1.09	5.79	5.44	1.28
9.28	1.54	2.18	6.02	10.88	1.29
13.91	1.46	3.27	6.27	16.32	1.21
18.55	1.46	4.35	6.02	21.76	1.18
23.19	1.57	4.64	60.2	27.20	1.18
27.83	1.51	9.28	6.27	32.64	1.18
32.47	1.55	13.91	6.98		
37.10	1.55	18.55	6.68		
		23.19	6.82		
		27.83	6.90		

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF ALKALI.

$[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[SCN^-] = 0.0928 M$; $\mu = 2.0$

$Os(VIII) = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$

$[OH^-] M$	$10^8 k(\text{min}^{-1})$	$10^8 k/[OH^-] M^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$
0.50	1.18	2.36
0.72	1.60	2.22
0.93	1.95	2.10
1.15	2.44	2.12
1.36	2.95	2.17
1.58	3.27	2.07
1.79	3.66	2.04
1.94	4.27	2.20

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF NEUTRAL SALTS.

$[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[OH^-] = 0.50 M$; $[SCN^-] = 9.28 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[Os(VIII)] = 7.4 \times 10^{-6} M$; $T = 35^\circ$

$10^4 k \times (\text{min}^{-1})$

Concentration of the Salt	KCl	NaCl	LiCl
(M)			
1.0	5.91	3.94	2.73
1.5	8.74	4.52	2.89
2.0	12.04	4.72	3.20
2.5	16.16	6.68	3.75
3.0	19.19	7.68	4.45

The effect of variation of ionic strength was studied in the range of 0.5 to 3.0μ . It was found that the rate increased with increasing ionic strength. However, it was known that reactant systems involving high charges, were liable to exhibit specific ion effects. Large specific cation effect was observed (Table 5) in the order $K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$. The specific anion effects were found to have little influence on the rate. The effects of divalent or polyvalent cations could not be studied as they resulted in the formation of precipitates, in the present investigation.

The kinetics were followed at the temperatures 23°, 30°, 35° and 45° in the range of 23°-45° and the average value of ΔH^\ddagger was 18.0 ± 0.5 Kcal. mole⁻¹. The experimental results conform to the following rate law.

$-d [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]/dt = k[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] [\text{OH}^-] \text{Os(VIII)}$
The following mechanism may be suggested.

The rate law was obtained by applying equilibrium treatment to slow step (2). The absorbance values in wave length region of 280-350 nm. of the mixture of hexacyanoferrate (III) and Osmium (VIII) in alkaline medium were not additive and decreased with time. This suggests a possible complex formation between hexacyanoferrate (III) and Osmium (VIII). Formation of such a complex has also been postulated previously^{1,5}. The Osmium (VIII) catalyzed oxidation of thiocyanate by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) is believed to proceed through the complex formation between $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ and Os (VIII), in a slow and rate determining step (2). Reaction (3) appears to be faster than the reaction (2) although it is a bimolecular reaction between similarly charged ions; it is probably highly exothermic^{2,9}. $\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$ was reported to be an unstable intermediate of Os(VIII) in alkaline medium^{3,9}.

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